

Use Case Application

Global Fish Tracking System

FOR
BY

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Development Seed

VERSION
DATE

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Introduction

This document links to the application code for the Global Fish Tracking Software (GFTS) DestinE Platform use case, and provide a direct link to the running application.

Use Case Backend Application

The use case application software is released continuously under an Apache 2.0 license and can be accessed and downloaded through GitHub using the following link

https://github.com/destination-earth/DestinE_ESA_GFTS

Use Case Frontend Application

The frontend of the use case application is released continuously under an MIT license and can be accessed and downloaded through GitHub using the following link:

<https://github.com/developmentseed/gfts/>

The use case application can be accessed through the services listing of the DestinE platform or by using the following direct link (login through DestinE will still be required).

<https://gfts.developmentseed.org/>